

**How important are holiday trips in
preventing loneliness? Evidence for people
without and with self-reported moderate and
severe disabilities**

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Abstract:

This study analyses the relationship between holiday trips and loneliness for people without and with self-reported disabilities (differentiating between moderate and severe disabilities limiting their daily activities) in Germany. Since loneliness is not only observed at older ages, we are particularly interested in exploring possible age differences in this relationship. Using data taken from the German Socio-Economic Panel for the year 2013 and applying a three-item version of the UCLA Loneliness Scale, we found that holiday trips contribute to reducing the levels of loneliness reported by all individuals, and that this reduction is even higher for people with self-reported disabilities (males and females) who are severely limited in their daily activities. However, the positive effects of holiday trips on loneliness did differ by age groups. The loneliness scores of people who have limiting disabilities in the 40-64 age group showed the greatest reduction as compared to those reported for people without self-reported disabilities. From a public policy and management perspective, the promotion of full access and participation of people with disabilities as active travellers within the tourism industry must be aimed at reducing their levels of loneliness and increasing their social tourism opportunities and experiences.

Keywords: UCLA loneliness scale; health status; daily activities.

Introduction

Loneliness has become a significant public social and health issue, with important implications for all economic sectors and industries (Gerst-Emerson and Jayawardhana, 2015). For example, the government in the United Kingdom in 2018 created its “Ministry of Loneliness” to address this growing problem through a set of initial commitments aimed at reducing loneliness in society in general, and particularly among those people at greater risk of suffering loneliness (Daley, 2018). According to Peplau and Perlman (1982) and Perlman and Peplau (1984), loneliness is the discrepancy between desired and

actual quantity and quality of social relations; Loneliness is a *subjective* experience (not synonymous with objective social isolation), and is *aversive* (i.e. unpleasant and distressing). Previous studies find that loneliness can predict mental health issues, symptoms of depression, heart disease, and blood pressure problems, as well as higher utilization of health care services (e.g. Heikkinen and Kauppinen, 2004; Cacioppo, Hughes, Waite, Hawkley, and Thisted, 2006; Wilson et al., 2007; Luanaigh and Lawlor, 2008; Hawkley, Thisted, Masi, and Cacioppo, 2010; Gerst-Emerson and Jayawardhana, 2015; and Valtorta et al., 2016). Although loneliness is often associated with the elderly, the reality is that it affects individuals of all ages (Luhman and Hawkley, 2016), and some individuals are prone to loneliness such as, for example, people with disabilities (Dykstra, Van Tilburg, and De Jong, 2005; Constanca, Ayis, and Ebrahim, 2006; Korporaal et al., 2008). The issue of loneliness is particularly relevant for people with disabilities because disability is associated with a reduction of autonomy, independence, self-determination, and self-development (Korporaal et al., 2008; Wullink, Widdershoven, Van Schrojenstein, Metsemakers, and Dinant, 2009), which leads to decreased opportunities for social participation in daily life. Within this context, leisure activities in general and holiday trips in particular may play an important role in preventing loneliness among people with disabilities, thanks to their beneficial effects on enhancing personal development, self-esteem, independence, social inclusion, and overall quality of life (Kastenholz et al. 2015). However, most people with disabilities are excluded from general leisure and tourism activities (Neal, Uysal, and Sirgy, 2007), and this fact has a significant and negative impact on their life satisfaction scores (Pagan, 2015a, 2015b). A look at the existing empirical literature reveals a lack of studies analysing the particular association of holiday trips with loneliness for the case of people with disabilities. According to McCabe (2009), “more systematic research is needed on measures of

benefits of holidays and on the impacts of social tourism so that comparative research can be undertaken (pp. 684)’’.

The aim of this study is to investigate how participation in holiday trips and its level of frequency or intensity contribute to reducing the loneliness scores reported by people with disabilities as compared to people without disabilities. An important novelty of this study is the possibility to differentiate within the disabled population between those individuals who have a moderate disability and those with a severe disability that limits their daily activities. This possibility allows us to follow the “*social model*” of disability as a framework wherein disability is not an attribute of the individual, but rather a complex collection of conditions, many of which are created by the social environment (Oliver, 1983). In addition, this study adopts the concept of “*social tourism*” defined by the International Organisation of Social Tourism (ISTO) which can be considered as an extraordinary opportunity for low-income groups (such as people with disabilities) to obtain unplanned learning, positive behaviour change, and further integration into society (Minnaert, Maitland, and Miller, 2011; Minnaert, 2012; Minnaert, 2014). Although there is abundant literature on the positive relationship between tourism and quality of life for all individuals (see, for example the work of Uysal, Sirgy, Woo, and Kim (2016) for an extensive and detailed revision of this previous literature), to our knowledge there are only a pair of empirical studies that have found similar results for people with disabilities (e.g. Pagan, 2015a, 2015b). However, our study is the first attempt to investigate the effects on holiday trips on loneliness for people with disabilities. In this regard and reviewing the previous literature on happiness, we find that indeed loneliness is one of the strongest and most robust predictors of life satisfaction (e.g. Cacioppo et al., 2006; Steverink and Lindenberg, 2006; Mauss et al., 2012; and Saygin, Akdeniz, and Deniz, 2015), i.e. the higher the loneliness levels, the lower the life satisfaction scores. If

participation in holiday trips enhances perceived social support and self-esteem, and these latter have been found to be strong predictors to reduce loneliness (Yildiz and Karadas, 2017), this reduction will increase life satisfaction as well. Therefore, loneliness may be seen as an important mediator/predictor between holiday trips and life satisfaction.

However, analysis of the relationship between loneliness and life satisfaction is quite complicated because there may be potential mutual influence between them (Cacioppo et al., 2006). For example, happiness itself can lead to obtaining positive rewards, including a higher number of social relations (Lyubomirsky, King, and Diener, 2005). However and according to VanderWeele, Hawkey, and Cacioppo (2012), life satisfaction reflects “a *positive* state that motivates people to continue what they are doing to *maintain this state*, ..., whereas loneliness is an *aversive* state that evolved as a signal-like physical pain, hunger, and thirst-to *change behaviour* (pp. 782)”. They also point out that loneliness may affect life satisfaction through its effects on emotions and moods, whereas life satisfaction itself may impact both objective and subjective aspects of social relationships. In addition, Mauss, Savino, Anderson, Weisbuch, and Tamir (2012) find that the pursuit of happiness might make people lonely, i.e., “*wanting* to be happy may sometimes have opposite effects than *being* happy, which often leads to positive social outcomes (pp. 911)”. These important differences between both concepts makes this study relevant and pertinent within the existing literature on leisure activities in general, and holiday trips in particular. In this sense, holiday trips may become effective tools to change the behaviour of individuals with disabilities and lower their loneliness scores.

Within this context, we are interested in testing the following hypothesis: Although the participation in holiday trips contributes to reducing all individuals’ loneliness scores, people with disabilities (especially those with severe disabilities) have a more significant reduction in their loneliness scores compared to people without disabilities. We theorize

that the benefits of participating in holiday trips can help provide stronger social relationships, better physical and mental health, improvement in quality of life, an opportunity to stay active, and as a result, a reduction in loneliness for all individuals (first part of hypothesis). At the same time, for people with disabilities (especially for those severely limited in their daily activities), holiday trips may become a crucial means to recover health status (e.g. reducing stress and depression, or being included within rehabilitation processes), self-esteem, self-identity, confidence, independence, family and social capital, and socialisation (second part of hypothesis). For this purpose, we have used data taken from the German Socioeconomic Panel (GSOEP) for the year 2013 (the only wave with available data on loneliness), and have estimated ordinary least square models (OLS) on loneliness which allows us to control for a set of variables (or characteristics) simultaneously. To check the robustness of our results, we have also run our regressions for three different age groups (i.e. <40 years, 40 to 64 years, and >64 years).

Materials and methods

Sample

This study uses data taken from the German Socioeconomic Panel (GSOEP), a large panel data (first started in 1984, with around 30,000 respondents and 11,000 households interviewed every year) which provides information from private households on individual and household characteristics (e.g. age, gender, education, household composition, employment, income sources, health indicators, and social capital measures). Despite the longitudinal nature of the GSOEP, we only use data collected in 2013 because it is the first time wherein our measure of loneliness is available. We restricted our sample to individuals aged 16 or over. After selecting respondents with valid information on all variables analysed, the final samples consist of 8,290 and 9,334

males and females, respectively. We also apply cross-sectional sample weights in our descriptive analysis in order to reflect population characteristics and correct for the possible lack of representativeness of the sample.

Measures

The GSOEP questionnaire for 2013 includes a set of questions on how often individuals take part in leisure activities such as going out for dinner or a drink, visiting or being visited by neighbours, friends, family members and relatives, attending religious events, watching TV/video, listening to the radio and *going on an excursion or short trip*. We have called this last leisure activity “*holiday trips*”. The possible responses to these questions are: daily, at least once a week, at least once a month, seldom and never. According to Pagan (2015b), “the wording of these questions and possible answers have slightly changed over the years: in the 1990 and 1995 waves of the GSOEP the category *holiday trips* was labelled *outings or short trips*. In 1998, the word *excursions* was included in this category. In 2003 and 2008 the category was labelled as *go(ing) on a trip or short holidays* (pp. 528)”. Due to the low number of people with severe and moderate self-reported disabilities for the first response “*daily*” who take part in an excursion or short trip, we have merged the first two responses into one, i.e. “*daily/weekly*”. Similar to Becchetti, Ricca, and Pelloni (2012), we have recoded all answers and have created a continuous variable “*holiday trips*” that takes the following values: 0=never, 1=seldom, 2=at least once a month, and 3=daily/weekly. Therefore, this variable ranges from 0 to 3, where a higher value indicates more intense participation in going on an excursion or short trip.

Loneliness is measured by using a three-item version of the UCLA Loneliness Scale (Russell, 1996), which has been recently used and validated in the existing literature on loneliness (e.g. Luo, Hawkey, Waite, and Cacioppo, 2012; Hawkey, Duvoisin, Ackva,

Murdoch, and Luhmann, 2015; Malter and Börsch-Supan, 2015; Niedzwiedz et al., 2016), and does not use direct questions about loneliness but assesses loneliness indirectly, reducing the stigma and potential biased responses from disadvantageous individuals (e.g. people with disabilities) who are more likely to underreport loneliness by a direct approach (Shiovitz-Ezra and Ayalon, 2012; Nicolaisen and Thorsen, 2014). Hawkley et al. (2015) confirm the validity of this measure, and introduce for the first time in the GSOEP questionnaire the following three questions: “a) *How often do you miss the company of other people?*; b) *How often do you feel left out?*, and; c) *How often do you feel socially isolated?* (Very often, often, sometimes, seldom and never)”. Similar to Luhman and Hawkley (2016), our variable “*loneliness*” is the mean value of the responses to these three questions, with the possible answers being recoded as follows: 0= never, 1= seldom, 2= sometimes, 3= often, and 4= very often. Namely, loneliness is measured with a scale that takes values from 0 (no loneliness) to 4 (high degree of loneliness).

Consistent with the previous literature (e.g. DeLeire, 2001; Gannon, 2005; Gannon and Munley, 2009; Jones, Latreille, and Sloane, 2006; Pagan 2011), our self-reported disability measure is based on two questions included in the GSOEP questionnaire for 2013: “*Do you have a health problem that limits you in normal everyday life?* (Yes, severely/Yes, somewhat/No, not at all)”. Those who answer “No, not at all” can be defined as people without disabilities. On the other hand, those individuals who respond “Yes, severely” or “Yes, somewhat” are also questioned: “*Have you had this health problem for more than half a year?* (Yes/No)”. Those individuals who respond “No” to this second question are again considered as people without disabilities, whereas those answering “Yes” are defined as people with disabilities. However, and according to Gannon (2005), it is possible to differentiate two groups within the latter: a) Those reporting a health problem for more than half a year that *severely* limits their normal daily

activities; and b) those who report such a condition but state that it limits them but *somewhat* (i.e. moderately). Therefore, we can distinguish three possible groups: a) People without disabilities; b) People with disabilities, moderately limited, and c) People with disabilities, severely limited.

Statistical analysis

Since we only have data for the year 2013 and similar to Luhmann and Hawkey (2016), we have run OLS regressions breaking down by gender to estimate the relationship between loneliness, holiday trips and self-reported disability. As noted earlier, we have also re-estimated our model for three age groups reflecting different development stages of life (i.e. <40 years, 40 to 64 years, and >64 years) in order to detect age differences in the relevance of loneliness predictors, especially those measuring the intensity of participation in holiday trips and disability status. Limitations in our sample sizes for the people with severe disabilities have prevented us from using more narrow age groups (for example, for the younger group, <40 years). In this analysis, we include in our estimations those explanatory variables traditionally used in the existing literature on loneliness: age (and its square), years of education, having the German nationality, total number of persons living in the household, existence of children in the household, real household income (in logarithms), employment status (full-time, part-time, and not working), relationship status (single, living with partner, and living without partner) and region of residence.

We have also included a set of variables measuring individuals' social capital. Following Arezzo and Giudici (2017), social capital (SC) consists of two components: “*bonding SC*” (frequency of contacts with family members, friends, neighbours, and use of social online network) and “*bridging SC*” (frequency of participation in volunteering, sports and cultural activities, and religious events). After recoding the responses for these

leisure activities in the same way as our key variable “*holiday trips*” (i.e. 0=never, 1=seldom, 2=at least once a month, and 3=daily/weekly) and following Becchetti, Pelloni, and Rossetti (2008), we have created a Social Capital Indicator (SCI) for the bonding and bridging SC components by calculating simply the mean of the scores obtained for each leisure activity in the corresponding component. Finally, we have also included the total number of close friends as a quantitative measure of social contact (Luhman and Hawkey, 2016). As noted earlier, the lack of information in the GSOEP on the type of disability that individuals have limits the scope of this study. This is because we cannot carry out a deeper analysis of the effects of holiday trips on loneliness, for example, for people suffering mental disorders or mobility restrictions (i.e. those with a lower probability of taking part in holiday trips as compared to other disabilities). We have used the statistical package STATA 14 to obtain all our descriptive and estimation results.

Results

Descriptive analysis

Figure 1 shows the mean levels of loneliness reported by males and females by their level of participation in holiday trips and disability status. Overall we find that the existence of a negative relationship between loneliness and participation in holidays trips for all individuals. We also observe that people with self-reported disabilities (moderate and severe) report higher loneliness scores as compared to people without disabilities. However, these differences in loneliness by disability status are more significant (according to the 95% confidence intervals) when the frequency of participation in holiday trips is lower. For those individuals who “*never*” participate in holiday trips, the loneliness score for the category “*severe limited disabled*” is 1.63 and 1.61 points for males and females, respectively, whereas for their non-disabled counterparts it is 1.07 and

1.16 points (i.e. a differential of 0.56 and 0.45 points, respectively). There is also a loneliness differential for the categories “*seldom*” and “*monthly*” between people with self-reported disabilities (and also between the categories moderately and severely limited disabled, except for males with a “*monthly*” participation in holiday trips) and people without disabilities. In contrast, looking at the loneliness scores for those taking part in holiday trips “*daily/weekly*”, we do not find statistically significant differences by disability status for the male and female samples. Namely, the higher the participation in holiday trips, the lower the loneliness gap by disability status.

[Figure 1]

Econometric analysis

Table 1 shows the estimation results obtained after running OLS regressions on loneliness for the male and female samples, as well as the mean values and standard deviation of the explanatory variables used in the estimation process. First, we observe that the coefficient on the variable “*holiday trips*” is negative and significant at the 1% level in all samples, that is, a higher participation in holiday trips contributes to reducing the loneliness scores reported by all individuals (supporting part of our hypothesis). This reduction in terms of loneliness is even greater for females than males (-0.071 *versus* -0.038 points, respectively). According to the mean values, lower participation in holiday trips among females (1.027 points) in comparison with males (1.255 points) may explain this result. Consistent with the existing literature, we find that people with self-reported disabilities (both moderately and severely limited disabled) suffer from higher levels of loneliness as compared to people without disabilities, and they are even stronger if the individual has a severely limiting disability. In this latter case, for both samples the coefficient on the variable “*severe limited disabled*” is positive and significant at the 1% level with respect to the reference category “*non-disabled*”, and statistically higher than that obtained for

the category “*moderate limited disabled*”. Namely, people with severe disabilities (both males and females) are more likely to suffer from loneliness than people with moderate disabilities and people without disabilities. In addition and according to the mean values, 9.1% of males have a severe limiting disability, whereas 22.3% report a moderate limiting disability. For females, these percentages goes up to 10.7 and 24.8%, respectively.

[Table 1]

Looking at the interaction terms between “*holiday trips*” and disability status, we detect that only the coefficient on “*holiday trips * severe limited disabled*” is negative and significant at conventional levels (-0.152 and -0.105 points for males and females, respectively) with respect to the reference category. Therefore, only for males and females with severe disabilities does a more intense participation in holiday trips reduce statistically their levels of loneliness as compared to travellers without disabilities. This result confirms our hypothesis but only partly because this effect of holiday trips on loneliness is not found for those people who has moderate limiting disabilities. Despite the negative coefficient on “*holiday trips * severe limited disabled*” for males and females, the total effect of participation in holidays trips on loneliness for people with severe disabilities is 0.383 (= -0.038+0.573-0.152) and 0.361 points (= -0.071+0.537-0.105), i.e., that negative coefficient is not enough to compensate the strong impact of having a severe disability on loneliness (0.573 and 0.537 points for males and females, respectively). As for the remaining results shown in Table 1, it is worthwhile mentioning the age differences in loneliness, the importance of the variable measuring the number of close friends and the component “*bonding SC*” in the female sample to reduce loneliness, the negative relationship between real household income and loneliness, and how being single (only for males) and living without a partner contribute to increasing levels of loneliness.

Robustness check

We have re-estimated our model for three age groups (i.e. <40 years, 40 to 64 years, and >64 years) in order to test the relevance of loneliness predictors, especially those related to participation in holiday trips and disability status (and its corresponding interaction terms). According to Table 2, once again a higher participation in holiday trips reduces the levels of loneliness reported by males and females for all age groups and in line with our first part of our hypothesis, except for older males (>64 years). The magnitude of the significant coefficients on “*holiday trips*” is quite similar for all male subsamples, whereas for the female ones it is relatively higher for the younger group (<40 years) compared to the other two groups (40 to 64 years, and >64 years). Moreover, the mean values of variable “*holiday trips*” are greater for the younger samples (both males and female), i.e. the younger you are, the more you take part in holiday trips. Having a self-reported disability has a significant and positive impact on loneliness (except for young females), especially for those with severe limiting disabilities. Once again, these results are in line with those shown in Table 1. We also find a well-known and positive relationship between self-reported disability and age. For example, the percentage of males (females) with severe disabilities for the age group “<40 years” is 1.6% (1.9%), goes up to 8.8% (9.9%) for the age group “40 to 64 years”, and reaches 16.5% (21%) for the older group “>64 years”. A similar pattern by age groups is found for those individuals with moderate disabilities.

[Table 2]

However and looking at the interactions terms by age groups, we find that for males the coefficient on the interaction term “*holiday trips * severe limited disabled*” is again negative and significant at the 5% level but only for the last two age groups, “40 to 64 years” and “>64 years” (-0.165 and -0.142 points, respectively), indicating additional

reductions in loneliness if the person who takes holiday trips has a severe limiting disability. In contrast, for females the only significant coefficients on the interaction terms are found for middle-aged individuals (40 to 64 years) with moderate and severe disabilities (and with a similar magnitude, around -0.14 points). That is, for middle-aged females with moderate and severe disabilities, a more intense participation in holiday trips contributes to reducing their levels of loneliness as compared to their non-disabled counterparts. Overall, we find a nonlinear effect of holiday trips and disability status on loneliness by age, with our hypothesis only being valid for middle-aged males and females (40 to 64 years) and males who are severely disabled aged 64 or over.

Discussion

Our results show how more intense participation in holiday trips reduces the loneliness scores reported by all individuals. In addition, people with self-reported disabilities (moderate and severe) are more likely than people without disabilities to report higher loneliness scores. This result is consistent with the existing literature of loneliness and disability (e.g. Verstraten, Brinkmann, Stevens, and Schouten, 2005; Korporaal et al, 2008; Alma et al., 2011). We have also found that the higher the participation in holiday trips, the lower the loneliness gap by disability status. This result is quite relevant and consistent with our hypothesis, and may be explained by the fact that those people with self-reported disabilities (especially those with severe disabilities) who participate more intensely in holiday trips obtain a stronger and longer emotional connection with other travellers (e.g. family members, friends, and formal helpers), tourism staff and leisure organizations, as well as greater personal and social development (e.g. gaining confidence and self-esteem, obtaining health and rehabilitation benefits, improving social inclusion, independency and quality of life, and feeling less like as a “*object of care*”) as compared to those who have a lower or null participation in holiday trips (McCabe, 2009;

Blichfeldt and Nicolaisen, 2011; Small, Darcy, and Packer, 2012; Kastenholz, Eusebio, and Figueiredo, 2015; Bauer, 2018). Furthermore, we have found that the reduction in loneliness scores is markedly greater for males and females who have severe limiting disabilities (i.e. those reporting the highest levels of loneliness) as compared to people without disabilities. This latter finding corroborates the need and importance of taking into account in this type of analysis the degree of disability that the person has in order to detect possible differences in terms of loneliness between people with moderate and severe limiting disabilities. In addition, we have found significant age differences in terms of loneliness, especially for those travellers with moderate and severe disabilities aged 40-64.

One of the main limitation of this study is the lack of information in the GSOEP on the types of disability that individuals have. We may expect different effects of holiday trips on loneliness according to the type of disability (e.g. for people with mental health problems who usually suffer from strong levels of loneliness and social isolation). Furthermore, the use of cross-sectional data (only for the year 2013) limits the scope of this study. The existence of longitudinal information would allow us to carry out a dynamic analysis, for example, on the effects of holiday trips before, during and after the disability onset on loneliness. Apart from this possible future research, it would be also interesting to use national administrative data on legal disability and degree of disability, as well as datasets for other countries which permit to carry out a comparative analysis, and shed further light on the particular relationship between participation in holiday trips and loneliness for people with disabilities.

Conclusions

Using data drawn from the German Socio-Economic Panel for the year 2013, we have investigated how holiday trips contribute to reducing the levels of loneliness reported by

people with self-reported disabilities as compared to people without disabilities. One significant novelty of this study as compared to previous studies on disability and loneliness is the possibility to differentiate within the disabled sample those people who have a moderate limiting disability from those with a severe limiting disability. Since there is no information on the type of disability that the person has in the GSOEP, this differentiation of the disabled population enables us to embrace the social model of disability (e.g. Shaw and Coles, 2004; Gannon and Munley, 2009; Pagan, 2012), control for the heterogeneity of the disabled population in a better way, and identify and compare the effects of holiday trips on loneliness (in our case) taking into account the degree of disability for those who suffer from limiting disabilities. Following the social model of disability allow us to treat individuals with self-reported disabilities as people with disabilities for future strategies, policies, programs, etc. Thanks to this information, we have found that holiday trips contributed to reducing all individuals' loneliness scores, but for travellers (males and females) with severe self-reported disabilities this reduction is even greater as compared to travellers without disabilities as they participate more intensely in holiday trips.

No one is immune to feelings of loneliness, but being disabled often leads to being isolated from society as a whole. Recently, loneliness and stress have been cited as the two main characteristics of people living with a disability in an inequitable society, which likewise points to the urgent need to carry out more research on the strong and clear connection between disability and loneliness (Olsen, 2018). Despite the fact that disability can take many forms and different typologies (e.g. short *versus* long-term health conditions, visual and hearing impairments, etc.), there is no doubt that it strongly affects participation of individuals in many of life's activities such as, for example, being an active tourist/traveller (e.g. Darcy, 2002; Shaw and Coles, 2004; Yau, McKercher, and

Packer, 2004; Pagan, 2012 and 2015b). Apart from the increasing debate on the need to remove all barriers faced by people with disabilities within the tourism and transport industry (e.g. Burnett and Baker, 2001; Eichhorn and Buhalis, 2007; Darcy, Cameron, and Pegg, 2010; Lee, Agarwal, and Kim, 2012; and Tutuncu, 2018), our results have clearly shown that people with severe self-reported disabilities face the highest levels of loneliness, and how holiday trips can contribute to alleviating it. A recent report from the British Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (2018) points out that “recognition of loneliness is the first step to addressing it (pp. 50)”. To do this, they mention that it is crucial for policy makers (e.g. government and local authorities), economic sectors (e.g. health, leisure and transport industries), the voluntary sector and community groups (e.g. disability organizations, and social workers) to all work together to raise awareness of loneliness (e.g. improving access to information, extending good practices and encouraging knowledge sharing on tackling loneliness), and build connections to create stronger and more integrated communities (e.g. using digital tools and infrastructure). These strategies and actions could help the tourism industry to create accessible and inclusive environments for travellers with disabilities. For example and according to Sirgy, Kruger, Lee, and Grace (2011), the design of specific tourism programs for people with disabilities can contribute to enhancing rest and relaxation, and to maximising tourists’ experience in terms of happiness and social relations, thereby resulting in a reduction in loneliness.

Furthermore, social tourism plays a crucial role in supporting the personal and interpersonal development of tourists with disabilities, increasing their levels of self-esteem, confidence, and independence, building relationships with fellow tourists, and setting new priorities in life that contribute to reducing their levels of loneliness and increasing their life satisfaction. To achieve this, providers of social tourism must offer

the most tailored-made and cost-effective tourism product to each individual with disabilities, taking into account their previous travel experience, as well as their specific needs and expectations before departure (Minnaert, 2014). For example, the IMSERSO Holiday Program for the Spanish elderly has enabled all Spanish-resident pensioners (most of them disabled) to benefit from cheaper holidays in Spain, participate in active aging programs, avoid situations of dependence, increase their social relations, and reduce loneliness, while at the same time boosting economic activities and employment in many sectors (especially during the low season).

References

- Alma, M., Van der Mei, S., Feitsma, W., Groothoff, J., Van Tilburg, T., & Suurmeijer, T. (2011). Loneliness and self-management abilities in the visually impaired elderly. *Journal of Aging and Health*, 23(5), 843-861.
- Arezzo, M., & Giudici, C. (2017). Social capital and self-perceived health among European older adults. *Social Indicators Research*, 130(2), 665-685.
- Bauer, I. (2018). When travel is a challenge: Travel medicine and the 'dis-abled' traveller. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 22(March-April), 66-72.
- Becchetti, L., Pelloni, A., & Rossetti, F. (2008). Relational goods, sociability and happiness. *Kyklos*, 61(3), 343-363.
- Becchetti, L., Ricca, E., & Pelloni, A. (2012). The relationship between social leisure and life satisfaction: causality and policy implications. *Social Indicators Research*, 108, 453-490.
- Blichfeld, B., & Nicolaisen, J. (2011). Disabled travel: not easy, but doable. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 14 (1), 79-102.
- British Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (2018). A connected society: A strategy for tackling loneliness – laying the foundations for change. Available at:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/750909/6.4882_DCMS_Loneliness_Strategy_web_Update.pdf.

- Burnett, J., & Baker, H. (2001). Assessing the travel-related behaviors of the mobility-disabled consumer. *Journal of Travel Research*, 40(1), 4-11.
- Cacioppo, J., Hughes, M., Waite, L., Hawkley, L., & Thisted, R. (2006). Loneliness as a specific risk factor for depressive symptoms: Cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses. *Psychology and Aging*, 21, 140-151.
- Constanca, P., Ayis, S., & Ebrahim, S. (2006). Psychological distress, loneliness and disability in old age. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 11(2), 221-32.
- Daley, J. (2018), The U.K. Now Has a ‘Minister for Loneliness.’ Here’s Why It Matters,” Smithsonian.com, published January 19, 2018, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/minister-loneliness-appointed-united-kingdom-180967883/>.
- Darcy, S. (2002). Marginalised participation: physical disability, high support needs and tourism. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 9, 61-72.
- Darcy, S., Cameron, B., & Pegg, S. (2010). Accessible tourism and sustainability: A discussion and case study. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 18(4), 515-537.
- DeLeire, T. (2001). Changes in wage discrimination against people with disabilities: 1984-1993. *Journal of Human Resources*, 36, 144-158.
- Dykstra, P., Van Tilburg, T., & De Jong, J. (2005). Gender and marital-history differences in emotional and social loneliness among Dutch older adults. *Canadian Journal on Aging*, 23, 141-155.
- Eichhorn, V., & Buhalis, D. (2007). The accessibility requiring market in Europe: Socially and economically important. *e-Review of Tourism Research*, 5(2), 34-36.
- Gannon, B. (2005). A dynamic analysis of disability and labour force participation in Ireland 1995-2000. *Health Economics*, 4(9), 925-938.

- Gannon, B., & Munley, M. (2009). Age and disability: explaining the wage differential. *Social Science & Medicine*, 69, 47-55.
- Gerst-Emerson, K., & Jayawardhana, J. (2015). Loneliness as a public health issue: the impact of loneliness on health care utilization among older adults. *American Journal of Public Health*, 105(5), 1013-1019.
- Hawkey, L., Thisted, R., Masi, C., & Cacioppo, J. (2010). Loneliness predicts increased blood pressure: five-year cross-lagged analyses in middle-aged and older adults. *Psychology and Aging*, 25(1), 132-141.
- Hawkey, L., Duvoisin, R., Ackva, J., Murdoch, J., & Luhmann, M. (2015). Loneliness in older adults in the USA and Germany: Measurement invariance and validation. *Working Paper Series, NORC at the University of Chicago*, Paper 2015-002.
- Heikkinen, R., & Kauppinen, M. (2004). Depressive symptoms in late life: A 10-year follow-up. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 38 (3), 239-250.
- Jones, M., Latreille, P., & Sloane, P. (2006). Disability, gender and the British labour market. *Oxford Economics Papers*, 58, 407-449.
- Kastenholz, E., Eusebio, C., & Figueiredo, E. (2015). Contributions of tourism to social inclusion of persons with disability. *Disability & Society*, 30 (8), 1259-1281.
- Korporaal, M., Broese van Groenou, M., & van Tilburg, T. (2008). Effects of own and spousal disability on loneliness among older adults. *Journal of Aging and Health*, 20(3), 306-325.
- Lee, B., Agarwal, S., & Kim, H. (2012). Influences of travel constraints on the people with disabilities' intention to travel: An application of Seligman's helplessness theory. *Tourism Management*, 33(3), 569-579.
- Luanaigh, C., & Lawlor, B. (2008). Loneliness and the health of older people. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 23 (12) 1213-1221.

- Luo, Y., Hawkey, L., Waite, L., & Cacioppo, J. (2012). Loneliness, health, and mortality in old age: a national longitudinal study. *Social Science and Medicine*, 74, 907-914.
- Luhmann, M., & Hawkey, L. (2016). Age differences in loneliness from late adolescence to oldest old age. *Developmental Psychology*, 52(6), 943-959.
- Lyubomirsky, S., King, L., & Diener, E. (2005). The benefits of frequent positive affect: Does happiness lead to success? *Psychological Bulletin*, 131, 803-855.
- Malter, F., & Börsch-Supan, A. (2015). *SHARE Wave 5: Innovations & Methodology*. MEA, Max Planck Institute for Social Law and Social Policy, Munich.
- Mauss, I., Savino, N., Anderson, C., Weisbuch, M., & Tamir, M. (2012). The pursuit of happiness can be lonely. *Emotion*, 12(5), 908-912.
- McCabe, S. (2009), 'Who needs a holiday? Evaluating social tourism'. *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol 36, No 4, pp 667-688.
- Minnaert, L., Maitland, R., & Miller, G. (2011). What is social tourism? *Current Issues in Tourism*, 14 (5), 403-415.
- Minnaert, L. (2012). Social tourism as opportunity for unplanned learning and behavior change. *Journal of Travel Research*, 51(5), 607-616.
- Minnaert, L. (2014). Social tourism participation: The role of tourism inexperience and uncertainty. *Tourism Management*, 40, 282-289.
- Neal, J., Uysal, M., & Sirgy, J. (2007). The effect of tourism services on travelers' quality of life, *Journal of Travel Research*, 46(2), 154-163.
- Nicolaisen, M., & Thorsen, K. (2014). Who are lonely? Loneliness in different age groups (18-81 years old), using two measures of loneliness. *International Journal of Aging & Human Development*, 78(3), 229-257.

- Niedzwiedz, C., Richardson, E., Tunstall, H., Shortt, N., Mitchell, R., & Pearce J. (2016). The relationship between wealth and loneliness among older people across Europe: Is social participation protective? *Preventive Medicine*, 91, 24-31.
- Oliver, M. (1983). *Social Work with Disabled People*. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- Olsen, J. (2018). Socially disabled: the fight disabled people face against loneliness and stress. *Disability & Society*, 33 (7), 1160-1164.
- Pagan, R. (2011). Ageing and disability: Job satisfaction differentials across Europe. *Social Science & Medicine*, 72, 206-215.
- Pagan, R. (2012). Time allocation in tourism for people with disabilities. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(3), 1514-1537.
- Pagan, R. (2015a). The contribution of holiday trips to life satisfaction: the case of people with disabilities. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 18(6), 524-538.
- Pagan, R. (2015b). The impact of holiday trips on life satisfaction and domains of life satisfaction: Evidence for German disabled individuals, *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(3), 359-379.
- Peplau, L., & Perlman, D. (1982). *Loneliness: A sourcebook of current theory, research, and therapy*. New York: Wiley.
- Perlman, D., & Peplau, L. (1984). Loneliness research: a survey of empirical findings. In L. Peplau and S. Goldston (Eds.), *Preventing the harmful consequences of severe and persistent loneliness*, US Government Print Office, 13-46.
- Russell, D. (1996). UCLA Loneliness Scale (Version 3): Reliability, Validity, and Factor Structure. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 66(1), 20-40.
- Saygin, Y., Akdeniz, S., & Deniz, M. (2015). Loneliness and interpersonal problem solving as predictors of subjective well-being, *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 5(1), 32-35.

- Shiovitz-Ezra, S., & Ayalon, L. (2012). Use of direct versus indirect approaches to measure loneliness in later life. *Research on Aging*, 34(5), 572-591.
- Shaw, G., & Coles, T. (2004). Disability, holiday making and the tourism industry in the UK: a preliminary survey. *Tourism Management*, 25, 397-403.
- Small, J., Darcy, S., & Packer, T. (2012). The embodied tourist experiences of people with vision impairment: Management implications beyond the visual gaze. *Tourism Management*, 33(4), 941-950.
- Sirgy, M., Kruger, P., Lee, D., & Grace, B. (2011). How does a travel trip affect tourists' life satisfaction? *Journal of Travel Research*, 50(3), 261-75.
- Steverink, N., & Lindenberg, S. (2006). Which social needs are important for subjective well-being? What happens to them with aging? *Psychology and Aging*, 21, 281-290.
- Tutuncu, O. (2018). Investigating the accessibility factors affecting hotel satisfaction of people with physical disabilities. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 65, 29-36.
- Uysal, M., Sirgy, M., Woo, E., & Kim, H. (2016). Quality of life (QOL) and well-being research in tourism. *Tourism Management*, 53(April), 244-261.
- Valtorta, N., Kanaan, M., Gilbody, S., Ronzi, S., & Hanratty, B. (2016). Loneliness and social isolation as risk factors for coronary heart disease and stroke: systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal observational studies. *Heart*, 102 (13), 1009-1016.
- VanderWeele, T., Hawkey, L., & Cacioppo J. (2012). On the reciprocal association between loneliness and subjective well-being. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 176(9), 777-784.
- Verstraten, P., Brinkmann, W., Stevens, N., & Schouten, J. (2005). Loneliness, adaptation to vision impairment, social support and depression among visually impaired elderly. *International Congress Series*, 1282, 317-321.

- Wilson, R., Krueger, K., Arnold, S., Schneider, J., Kelly, J., Barnes, L., Tang, Y., & Bennett, D. (2007). Loneliness and risk of Alzheimer disease. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 64(2), 234-240.
- Wullink, M., Widdershoven, G., Van Schrojenstein H, Metsemakers, J., & Dinant, G. (2009). Autonomy in relation to health among people with intellectual disability: a literature review. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 53(9), 816-826.
- Yau, M., McKercher, B., & Packer, T. (2004). Traveling with a disability. More than an access issue. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(4), 946-960.
- Yildiz, M., & Karadas, C. (2017). Multiple mediation of self-esteem and perceived social support in the relationship between loneliness and life satisfaction. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(3), 130-139.

Table 1. Loneliness regressions for males and females in Germany.

	MALES		FEMALES	
	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>
Holiday trips	1.255 (0.724)	-0.038*** (0.014)	1.027 (0.769)	-0.071*** (0.014)
Disability status:				
Moderate limited disabled (MLD)	0.223	0.162*** (0.041)	0.248	0.241*** (0.040)
Severe limited disabled (SLD)	0.091	0.573*** (0.058)	0.107	0.537*** (0.055)
Non-disabled (ND)	0.686	-	0.645	-
Interaction terms:				
Holiday trips * MLD	0.266	0.001 (0.027)	0.289	-0.040 (0.026)
Holiday trips * SLD	0.084	-0.152*** (0.043)	0.093	-0.105** (0.042)
Age	52 (17.9)	0.016*** (0.003)	52 (17.6)	-0.003 (0.003)
Age ²	3057 (1860.8)	-0.0002*** (3.09e-05)	3006 (1851.3)	-0.00006** (3.09e-05)
German nationality	0.959	-0.005 (0.045)	0.955	-0.140*** (0.041)
Years of education	11.950 (3.976)	0.0007 (0.002)	11.636 (3.863)	0.005** (0.002)
Household size	2.519 (1.194)	-0.006 (0.010)	2.457 (1.205)	-0.033*** (0.010)
Existence of children in the household	0.233	0.009 (0.025)	0.264	0.001 (0.025)
Log (real household income)	5.425 (0.550)	-0.076*** (0.017)	5.353 (0.549)	-0.082*** (0.017)
Bridging SC Index	0.931 (0.644)	-0.012 (0.013)	0.954 (0.645)	-0.023* (0.013)
Bonding SC Index	1.603 (0.664)	-0.016 (0.014)	1.656 (0.647)	-0.043*** (0.014)
Number of close friends	4.361 (3.993)	-0.013*** (0.002)	4.197 (3.336)	-0.026*** (0.002)
Relationship status:				
Single	0.189	0.198*** (0.029)	0.149	0.010 (0.029)
Living without partner	0.098	0.217*** (0.031)	0.195	0.147*** (0.025)
Living with partner (<i>reference</i>)	0.713	-	0.656	-
Employment status:				
Full-time	0.506	- (0.024)	0.246	- (0.024)
Part-time	0.092	-0.013 (0.030)	0.297	-0.083*** (0.021)
Not working (<i>reference</i>)	0.402	-	0.457	-
Regional dummies		Yes		Yes
<i>Constant</i>		1.157*** (0.130)		2.168*** (0.128)
Number observations		8,290		9,334
R-squared		0.098		0.113

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses, stars for significance levels. Individuals aged 16 or over: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.
Source: Author's calculations using the German Socio-Economic Panel (GSOEP) for the year 2013.

Table 2. Loneliness regressions for males and females by age groups in Germany.

	MALES		FEMALES		MALES		FEMALES		MALES		FEMALES	
	<40		<40		40-64		40-64		>64		>64	
	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>
Holiday trips	1.277 (0.697)	-0.049* (0.026)	1.286 (0.677)	-0.095*** (0.025)	1.252 (0.686)	-0.045** (0.021)	1.222 (0.683)	-0.054** (0.021)	1.241 (0.803)	0.002 (0.027)	1.096 (0.782)	-0.077** (0.030)
Disability status:												
Moderate limited disabled (MLD)	0.081	0.285** (0.111)	0.109	0.043 (0.119)	0.213	0.163** (0.064)	0.254	0.359*** (0.058)	0.364	0.132** (0.064)	0.375	0.163** (0.065)
Severe limited disabled (SLD)	0.016	0.558* (0.301)	0.019	0.056 (0.263)	0.088	0.594*** (0.095)	0.099	0.528*** (0.085)	0.165	0.524*** (0.081)	0.210	0.514*** (0.080)
Non-disabled (ND)	0.903		0.872		0.699		0.648		0.471		0.415	
Interaction terms:												
Holiday trips * MLD	0.093	-0.042 (0.078)	0.142	0.099 (0.078)	0.254	0.011 (0.045)	0.299	-0.138*** (0.040)	0.442	-0.014 (0.042)	0.421	0.026 (0.043)
Holiday trips * SLD	0.016	-0.344 (0.236)	0.022	0.345 (0.217)	0.082	-0.165** (0.072)	0.095	-0.140** (0.062)	0.146	-0.142** (0.056)	0.159	-0.075 (0.061)
<i>Constant</i>		0.559 (0.471)		1.254*** (0.460)		0.702 (0.659)		0.505 (0.698)		1.404 (1.880)		7.417*** (1.830)
Number observations	2,103		2,445		3,822		4,430		2,365		2,459	
R-squared	0.065		0.074		0.130		0.142		0.114		0.144	

Note: All regressions include the rest of the explanatory variables shown in Table 1. Robust standard errors in parentheses, stars for significance levels. Individuals aged 16 or over: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. **Source:** Author's calculations using the German Socio-Economic Panel (GSOEP) for the year 2013.